

Tutorial for using hydroPSO to calibrate the CemaNeige-GR6J model

Study area: Trancura River Basin, Chile

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1 A bit of history

When the development of `hydroPSO` (Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas, 2013) started in 2010, the R ecosystem for hydrological modelling was still relatively limited. To the best of our knowledge, `topmodel` was one of the few hydrological models fully implemented as an R function and available from CRAN. At that time, many operational and research hydrological models were still executed externally from R. For this reason, `hydroPSO` was designed as a model-independent optimisation framework able to calibrate command-line environmental models on different operating systems (e.g., GNU/Linux, Windows and macOS), while also supporting the optimisation of R functions in a global, population-based way rather than through local search only.

Since then, R has continued to gain relevance in the hydrological community, and several hydrological modelling tools are now available as R packages, even when some of them internally call compiled Fortran or C/C++ routines. Examples include `TUWmodel`, `airGR`, and `VIC5`. This evolution has made it increasingly important to provide calibration tools that are reproducible, scriptable and compatible with the broader R scientific-computing ecosystem.

This tutorial shows how to use `hydroPSO` $\geq 0.5-0$ to calibrate the snow-accounting `CemaNeige-GR6J` hydrological model using hydrometeorological data with the `hydroPSO` package. The example is intentionally reproducible and self-contained, but the workflow can be adapted to other catchments, other input data sources, and other R-based hydrological models with only moderate modifications to the data-preparation and model-wrapper sections.

2 Citation

This tutorial follows the structure of the vignettes showing how to use [hydroPSO to calibrate the TUWmodel](#) and [hydroPSO to calibrate the GR4J hydrological model](#), with the model-specific adaptations required by `CemaNeige-GR6J`. If you find this vignette useful, please cite it as:

Zambrano-Bigiarini, Mauricio (2026). Tutorial for using `hydroPSO` to calibrate the `CemaNeige-GR6J` hydrological model. doi:10.5281/zenodo.20481591. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20481591>.

3 Required hydroPSO version

This tutorial was developed for `hydroPSO` $\geq 0.5-0$, released in Github in March 2020. Although `hydroPSO` has always been able to optimise R functions, earlier versions were primarily designed for calibrating external models and did not store the complete simulation archive when calibrating R-based models. Since **v0.5-0**, `hydroPSO` is fully compatible with R-based hydrological and environmental models, including the storage of simulated time series required for diagnostic plotting, behavioural-parameter analysis and uncertainty assessment.

4 Objective

The main objective of this tutorial is to show how `hydroPSO` can be used to obtain an **acceptable** best parameter set for the `CemaNeige-GR6J` hydrological model and to generate the diagnostic material required to evaluate the calibration. The emphasis is methodological: model setup, wrapper-function design, parameter-space definition, calibration, verification, diagnostic plotting and uncertainty assessment. This document is not intended to provide a full theoretical treatment of hydrological calibration, sensitivity analysis or uncertainty analysis¹, nor an exhaustive interpretation of all hydrological results. Instead, it provides a reproducible workflow that hydrologists can adapt to their own catchments and research questions. Comments and questions are welcome.

¹Some basic references are provided throughout the text to guide readers who are less familiar with these topics.

5 hydroPSO

hydroPSO is a multi-platform, model-independent R package based on Particle Swarm Optimisation [PSO; Kennedy & Eberhart (1995)]. It was designed to support: *i*) model calibration; *ii*) parameter sensitivity analysis; and *iii*) post-calibration assessment of parameter sets and model simulations. The package can be used with external models controlled through PEST-like files, as well as with R functions such as those provided by `airGR`. It also supports parallel execution, which is particularly useful when the hydrological model is computationally demanding or when the calibration requires a large number of model evaluations.

PSO is a population-based stochastic optimisation technique in which a *swarm* of particles explores a bounded parameter space to maximise or minimise a user-defined objective function. Each particle represents a candidate parameter set. During the optimisation, particles update their positions and velocities using their own best previous positions and the best positions found by neighbouring particles. This makes PSO well suited to hydrological calibration problems, where objective-function surfaces are often non-linear, non-convex and affected by parameter interactions. The search continues until a stopping criterion is met, such as a maximum number of iterations or a convergence tolerance. For a detailed description of the hydroPSO implementation, see Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas (2013) and Zambrano-Bigiarini et al. (2013).

6 CemaNeige-GR6J hydrological model

The CemaNeige-GR6J model combines the daily lumped rainfall-runoff model GR6J with the CemaNeige snow-accounting routine. This combination is especially relevant for catchments where snow accumulation and melt modulate the seasonal partitioning of precipitation and therefore influence both high-flow and low-flow dynamics. Based on Poncelet et al. (2017), the following paragraphs provide a concise description of the GR6J structure and the CemaNeige routine.

GR6J is a daily lumped rainfall-runoff model developed to improve low-flow simulation while preserving the parsimony of the GR model family (Pushpalatha et al., 2011). It has three conceptual stores:

- 1) **production store**: used to compute the actual evapotranspiration (Es) and the water amount that reaches the routing store (Pr). It is described by its capacity, the $X1$ parameter (mm). Es and Ps are both computed based on $X1$ and the level in the store (S) and on the internal variables Pn and En , respectively.
- 2) **routing store**: used to reproduce part of the flow routing (routed flows). It is described by its capacity, the parameter $X3$ (mm). In every time step, the routed flows are independent of the soil moisture state and account for 90% of Pr .
- 3) **exponential store**: used to reproduce long recessions and low flows. It is controlled by the $X6$ parameter (mm), a base level in the store.

The **non-atmospheric exchange function** (L [mm d⁻¹]) represents water exchanges with groundwater aquifers or neighbouring catchments. It is controlled by $X2$ and $X5$ as a function of the filling rate of the routing store. The catchment response time is represented through **two unit hydrographs**, $UH1$ for routed flow and $UH2$ for direct flow, both controlled by the time-base parameter $X4$ (d). Streamflow volume is therefore mainly affected by the interaction among $X1$, $X2$ and $X5$, whereas temporal variability and recession behaviour are more strongly influenced by $X3$, $X4$ and $X6$, with additional contributions from $X1$. Consequently, model performance cannot be attributed mechanically to individual parameter values: the calibrated response emerges from interacting stores, exchange terms and routing components. A schematic representation of the GR6J model is provided in Figure 2 of Poncelet et al. (2017).

The CemaNeige snow-accounting routine is a parsimonious snow accumulation and melt module based on the degree-day concept (Valéry et al., 2010, 2014b). It uses elevation-band information to account for orographic gradients in snow processes and represents the snowpack through two parameters: Ctg , a dimensionless weighting coefficient controlling the thermal state of the snowpack, and Kf , a degree-day melt factor expressed in mm °C⁻¹ d⁻¹. Larger Ctg values increase the inertia of the snowpack thermal state, whereas larger Kf values produce faster melt rates when temperatures exceed the melt threshold.

The parameters used by **CemaNeige-GR6J** to represent the dominant hydrological and snow processes of a basin are summarised in Tables 1 and 2. Parameters **X1**, **X2**, **X3** and **X4** correspond to the rainfall-runoff structure and describe production storage, groundwater exchange, routing storage and unit-hydrograph timing, respectively (Perrin et al., 2003). Parameters **X5** and **X6** were introduced in the later GR5J/GR6J developments to improve the representation of groundwater exchange and low-flow dynamics (Pushpalatha et al., 2011). The two CemaNeige parameters, **Ctg** and **Kf**, describe the thermal state of the snowpack and the degree-day snowmelt rate, respectively (INRAE, 2023; Valéry et al., 2014a, 2014b).

The bounds used in this vignette are intentionally compact. They are intended to provide a stable, reproducible and computationally efficient calibration example for illustrating the use of **hydroPSO** with the **CemaNeige-GR6J** model. For this purpose, the classical GR parameter intervals remain appropriate because they restrict the search space to hydrologically plausible values while reducing the probability of poorly constrained or numerically inefficient optimisation runs. The CemaNeige bounds follow the standard formulation used in the INRAE GR modelling framework, where **Ctg** is constrained between 0 and 1 and **Kf** is generally treated as a degree-day melt factor within a narrow positive range (INRAE, 2023).

However, these vignette bounds should not be interpreted as universal parameter limits. Recent applications and large-sample studies indicate that broader ranges may be required when the model is applied to hydroclimatically diverse basins, steep mountain catchments, snow-dominated regimes, karstic or groundwater-influenced systems, or regionalisation and sensitivity-analysis experiments (Flores et al., 2021; Neri et al., 2020; Park et al., 2025). In particular, parameters related to routing storage, groundwater exchange and low-flow simulation (**X2**, **X3**, **X5** and **X6**) may show strong catchment dependence or weak identifiability, depending on the objective function, calibration period, flow regime and input data quality. Therefore, the broader ranges in Table 2 are recommended for exploratory calibration, sensitivity analysis, or transfer to basins with hydrological behaviour substantially different from the example used in this vignette.

Suggested compact parameter ranges

The parameter ranges in Table 1 are intended for the most typical applications rather than for exhaustive exploration of the full parameter space for all possible catchments. They provide compact, hydrologically plausible bounds that are suitable for demonstrating the use of **hydroPSO** with the **CemaNeige-GR6J** model in a reproducible and computationally efficient way. For the GR rainfall-runoff component, the ranges retain the classical GR-family calibration intervals commonly used as practical prior bounds for parsimonious daily rainfall-runoff modelling (Perrin et al., 2003; Pushpalatha et al., 2011). For the snow module, the **Ctg** and **Kf** ranges follow the standard CemaNeige formulation, where **Ctg** represents the inertia of the snowpack thermal state and **Kf** controls degree-day melt rates (INRAE, 2023; Valéry et al., 2014a, 2014b). These bounds help reduce unnecessary equifinality, avoid excessive computational cost, and keep the example focused on the calibration workflow rather than on a full sensitivity analysis.

ID	Description	Units	Dominant process	Compact parameter range
X1	Maximum capacity of the production store	mm	Soil moisture, evapotranspiration, percolation	[100, 1200]
X2	Groundwater exchange coefficient	mm d ⁻¹	Groundwater exchange, routing	[-5, 3]
X3	Maximum capacity of the routing store	mm	Routing, catchment storage	[20, 300]
X4	Time base of unit hydrograph UH1	d	Flow timing, peak-flow response	[1.1, 2.9]

ID	Description	Units	Dominant process	Compact parameter range
X5	Threshold controlling changes in the direction of groundwater exchange according to the routing-store state	-	Low flows, exchange dynamics	[-10, 10]
X6	Exponential store depletion coefficient	mm	Low flows, slow-flow recession	[0.01, 50]
Ctg	Weighting coefficient for the snow thermal state	-	Snowpack thermal inertia	[0.01, 1.00]
Kf	Degree-day melting factor	mm °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹	Snowmelt	[2.00, 6.00]

Table 1: Suggested parameter ranges for the ‘CemaNeige-GR6J’ calibration example used in this vignette.

Suggested parameter ranges for broader calibration

The broader ranges in Table 2 are recommended when the ranges provided in Table 1 did not produce acceptable results for your particular case study, or when the modelling objective is exploratory calibration, sensitivity analysis, model transfer to contrasting hydroclimatic regimes, or assessment of parameter equifinality. These parameter ranges are deliberately wider than those provided in Table 1 because several GR-family parameters; particularly those controlling groundwater exchange, routing storage, low-flow behaviour and response timing; may show strong catchment dependence or weak identifiability under different climates, physiographic settings, objective functions and data-quality conditions (Flores et al., 2021; Neri et al., 2020; Park et al., 2025). These broader intervals are therefore not intended as default bounds for every calibration, but as a pragmatic starting point for diagnosing whether the optimum is being constrained by overly narrow parameter limits. If the best-performing solution lies close to any lower or upper bound, the corresponding interval should be widened and the calibration repeated before interpreting the final parameter set.

ID	Description	Units	Dominant process	Broader parameter range
X1	Maximum capacity of the production store	mm	Soil moisture, evapotranspiration, percolation	[1, 3000]
X2	Groundwater exchange coefficient	mm d ⁻¹	Groundwater exchange, routing	[-50, 50]
X3	Maximum capacity of the routing store	mm	Routing, catchment storage	[1, 5000]
X4	Time base of unit hydrograph UH1	d	Flow timing, peak-flow response	[0.5, 10]

ID	Description	Units	Dominant process	Broader parameter range
X5	Threshold controlling changes in the direction of groundwater exchange according to the routing-store state	-	Low flows, exchange dynamics	[-50, 50]
X6	Exponential store depletion coefficient	mm	Low flows, slow-flow recession	[0.01, 500]
Ctg	Weighting coefficient for the snow thermal state	-	Snowpack thermal inertia	[0.00, 1.00]
Kf	Degree-day melting factor	mm °C ⁻¹ d ⁻¹	Snowmelt	[0.00, 10.00]

Table 2: Suggested broader parameter ranges for exploratory calibration, sensitivity analysis or application to basins with hydrological behaviour different from the vignette catchment.

In practice, the choice between Tables 1 and 2 should depend on the objective of the analysis. **Table 1 is recommended for the present vignette** because it keeps the hydroPSO search space compact, improves reproducibility and reduces unnecessary computational cost. **Table 2 is recommended when the aim is to evaluate parameter sensitivity**, explore equifinality, transfer the model to contrasting hydroclimatic regimes, or diagnose whether the optimum solution is being constrained by overly narrow parameter bounds. If the calibrated optimum is located close to any lower or upper bound, the corresponding parameter range should be widened and the calibration repeated before interpreting the resulting parameter set.

7 Installation

The latest stable versions of [hydroPSO](#) and [airGR](#) can be installed from CRAN as follows:

```
install.packages("hydroPSO")
install.packages("airGR")
```

Alternatively, the development version of [hydroPSO](#) can be installed from [GitHub](#):

```
if (!require(devtools)) install.packages("devtools")
#library(devtools)
#install_github("hzambran/hydroPSO")
```

The latest stable versions of [hydroTSM](#) and [hydroGOF](#) can also be installed from CRAN. These packages are used to manipulate hydrological time series and evaluate the performance of simulated streamflow.

```
#install.packages("hydroTSM")
#install.packages("hydroGOF")
```

8 Model set up

8.1 Loading required packages

The `hydroPSO` and `airGR` packages include all the data and main functions used in this analysis. The `hydroTSM` (Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2026b) and `hydroGOF` (Zambrano-Bigiarini, 2026a) packages are used here to manipulate the hydrological time series and to compute the modified Kling-Gupta efficiency [KGE'; Gupta et al. (2009); Kling et al. (2012)] used in the calibration step, respectively.

```
library(airGR)
library(hydroPSO)
library(hydroTSM)
library(hydroGOF)
```

8.2 General settings

The variable `model.drty` defines the parent directory where the outputs generated during model calibration, post-processing and verification will be stored.

```
# modify it according to your specific paths
#model.drty <- "/home/hzambran/GIT/vignettes/vignette_output/vignette_output"
model.drty <- "/Users/hzambran/GIT/vignettes/hydroPSO_vignettes/vignette_output"
```

The variable `PSO.drty.out` defines the directory where `hydroPSO` will write the calibration archive and its diagnostic figures. This path is passed through the `drty.out` element of the `control` argument in `hydroPSO`, ensuring that all PSO outputs are written to a controlled and reproducible location.

```
PSO.drty.out <- file.path(model.drty, "PSO.out")
```

The variable `Figures.drty.out` defines the directory used for figures generated outside the internal `hydroPSO` plotting routines, including calibration, verification and uncertainty-analysis plots.

```
Figures.drty.out <- file.path(model.drty, "Figures")
```

```
# If the output directory selected to store the figures does not exist, it is created:
if (!file.exists(Figures.drty.out)) dir.create(Figures.drty.out, recursive=TRUE)
```

The calibration and verification periods are defined below. Each period includes a one-year warm-up interval, which allows the model stores to evolve from their initial conditions before the goodness-of-fit measure is computed:

```
### Calibration period
Cal.Ini <- "1980-01-01"
Cal.Fin <- "1997-12-31"

### Verification period
Ver.Ini <- "1999-01-01"
Ver.Fin <- "2016-12-31"

### Starting date of the warm-up period, one for calibration and other for verification
Warmup.Ini.Cal <- "1979-01-01"
Warmup.Fin.Cal <- "1979-12-31"
Warmup.Ini.Ver <- "1998-01-01"
Warmup.Fin.Ver <- "1998-12-31"
```

8.3 Input data

The study area is a snow-influenced subcatchment of the Trancura River Basin, located in the Araucania Region of southern Chile. The catchment drains to the “Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco” streamflow station (COD.BNA: 9414001), providing a suitable example for demonstrating the joint calibration of rainfall-runoff and snow-accounting parameters.

To run `CemaNeige-GR6J`, daily catchment-mean precipitation, air temperature and potential evapotranspiration are required. For this example, daily precipitation (P [mm d^{-1}]), mean air temperature (T_{mean} [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]), potential evapotranspiration (PET [mm d^{-1}]) and observed streamflow (Q [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$]) for 1979-2016 were obtained from the CAMELS-CL dataset (Alvarez-Garreton et al., 2018). Precipitation corresponds to spatially averaged CR2MET values, whereas potential evapotranspiration was computed using the Hargreaves-Samani equation based on maximum and minimum air temperature.

These time series are distributed with `hydroPSO >= 0.5-0`, which makes the example fully reproducible. Users can replace them with local observations, gridded products or reanalysis-derived forcing data, provided that the variables are prepared at the required daily time step and in consistent units.

Specifying the catchment area, [m^2]:

```
Area.m2 <- 1415025887
```

Specifying the name and ID of the discharge station used as outlet of the study area (they will be used afterwards, in the title of some figures during the analysis of the calibration results):

```
Qobs.stationname <- "Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco"  
Qobs.ID <- "9414001"
```

Loading the daily meteorological input data (P , Temp, and PET) and the observed discharges at the outlet of the catchment as a single data.frame object, with values from 01-Jan-1979 to 31-Dec-2016:

```
data(Trancura9414001)
```

Creating individual time series of P , T_{mean} , PET and Q_{obs} :

```
dates <- Trancura9414001[, 1]  
P <- Trancura9414001[, 2]  
Tmean <- Trancura9414001[, 3]  
PET <- Trancura9414001[, 4]  
Qobs <- Trancura9414001[, 5]
```

When using `CemaNeige-GR6J`, catchment elevation information must be provided to represent the hypsometric distribution required by the snow module. According to `?CreateInputsModel`, the `HypsoData` argument is a numeric vector of 101 elevation values corresponding to the minimum elevation, the 1st to 99th percentiles, and the maximum elevation. If a DEM is available, these values can be computed with `hypsometric.values <- quantile(dem, probs=seq(0, 1, by=0.01))`. The following vector contains the hypsometric values for the Trancura antes de Llafenco River Basin, derived from a TanDEM-X DEM with 12.5 m spatial resolution.

```
hypsometric.values <-c(396.1, 396.1, 398.3, 408.3, 422.6, 442.6, 469.2, 495.0,  
520.4, 548.4, 573.5, 595.6, 618.3, 640.7, 662.0, 681.4, 703.7, 726.0, 747.2,  
769.1, 790.2, 810.5, 830.3, 847.7, 864.7, 880.3, 895.1, 909.9, 924.5, 937.7,  
951.9, 966.1, 980.6, 994.7, 1008.4, 1022.3, 1035.8, 1048.6, 1061.7, 1073.9,  
1086.0, 1098.7, 1111.3, 1123.5, 1133.4, 1143.7, 1154.4, 1165.2, 1176.0, 1186.7,  
1197.2, 1207.5, 1217.8, 1228.0, 1238.1, 1248.3, 1258.5, 1269.1, 1279.9, 1290.7,  
1301.2, 1311.7, 1321.6, 1331.1, 1341.3, 1351.4, 1361.4, 1371.5, 1381.4, 1391.7,  
1402.4, 1413.3, 1424.2, 1435.3, 1446.7, 1458.5, 1470.7, 1482.5, 1494.8, 1507.2,  
1520.4, 1534.2, 1548.4, 1563.6, 1579.2, 1595.4, 1612.2, 1629.7, 1648.4, 1668.1,  
1683.1, 1703.0, 1724.4, 1747.6, 1773.4, 1805.9, 1841.9, 1892.6, 1970.9, 2129.7,  
3769.1)
```

The optional argument `NLayers` defines the number of elevation layers used by the `CemaNeige` module. The default value is 5, as shown below:

```
NLayers <- 5
```

Observed discharge is not required to **run** `CemaNeige-GR6J`, but it is required to **calibrate** the model. The observations must have the same temporal resolution as the simulations so that the selected goodness-of-fit metric can be computed consistently.

Transforming the previously created numeric values and their corresponding dates into zoo objects:

```
dates      <- as.Date(dates)
P.zoo      <- zoo(P, dates)
Tmean.zoo  <- zoo(Tmean, dates)
PET.zoo    <- zoo(PET, dates)
Qobs.zoo   <- zoo(Qobs, dates)
```

Daily discharges simulated by `CemaNeige-GR6J` are expressed in mm/day, but the previously loaded observed discharges are in m³/s. Therefore, in order to correctly compare the observations (m³/s) with the simulated values obtained from `CemaNeige-GR6J` (in mm/day) it is necessary to convert the observed discharges from m³/s to mm/day:

```
# 1 day = 86400 s
Qobs.zoo <- (Qobs.zoo * 1000 * 86400) / Area.m2
```

Plotting the full time series of meteorological input data (P, Tmean, PET) and the observed discharges (Qobs):

```
par(mfrow=c(4,1), mar = c(2, 3.5, 1, 1), oma=c(0, 0, 0, 0), mgp=c(2, 0.75, 0) )
plot(P.zoo , xlab="Time", col="lightblue", main="Precipitation" , ylab="P [mm/day]")
grid()
plot(Tmean.zoo, xlab="Time", col="red", main="Mean air temperature" , ylab="Temp [°C]")
grid()
plot(PET.zoo , xlab="Time", col="darkgreen", main="Potential evaporation", ylab="PET [mm/day]")
grid()
plot(Qobs.zoo , xlab="Time" , col="blue" , main="Observed streamflows" , ylab="Q, [mm/day]" )
grid()
```


Figure 1: Daily values of precipitation, air temperature, potential evapotranspiration and streamflows for the Trancura River Basin during the 1970-2016 time period.

8.4 Model parameters

Although not strictly required by `hydroPSO`, assigning names to the `airGR` model parameters improves the readability of the calibration results and the diagnostic plots. The lower and upper bounds define the admissible parameter space explored by PSO and should therefore be chosen consistently with the objective of the analysis.

One option is to use compact ranges based on the classical GR-family calibration intervals and the standard CemaNeige bounds:

```
names <- c("X1", "X2", "X3", "X4", "X5", "X6", "Ctg", "Kf")
lower <- c( 100, -5, 20, 1.1, -10, 0.01, 0.01, 2.00)
upper <- c(1200, 3, 300, 2.9, 10, 50.0, 1.0, 6.00)

names(lower) <- names
names(upper) <- names
```

Alternatively, very wide transformed ranges can be used for exploratory analysis, although they may increase computation time and equifinality:

```
boundaries <- matrix(c(+9.99, +9.99, +9.99, +9.99, +9.99, +9.99, +9.99, +9.99,
                      -9.99, -9.99, -9.99, -9.99, -9.99, -9.99, -9.99, -9.99),
                    ncol = 8, byrow = TRUE)

boundaries.GR6J <- TransfoParam_GR6J(ParamIn = boundaries[, 1:6], Direction = "TR")
boundaries.CemaNeige <- TransfoParam_CemaNeige(ParamIn = boundaries[, 7:8], Direction = "TR")

lower <- c(boundaries.GR6J[2, ], boundaries.CemaNeige[2, ])
upper <- c(boundaries.GR6J[1, ], boundaries.CemaNeige[1, ])

names(lower) <- names
names(upper) <- names
```

However, a very wide parameter range may require a very large number of model runs before an acceptable *best* parameter set is found. It may also allocate many particles to hydrologically implausible regions of the search space, reducing the efficiency of the calibration experiment.

For this vignette, we use an intermediate set of bounds that is wider than the classical compact range for selected hydrological parameters but still constrained enough to keep the calibration stable and computationally efficient:

```
names <- c("X1", "X2", "X3", "X4", "X5", "X6", "Ctg", "Kf")
lower <- c( 0, -100, 0, 0, -10, 0.01, 0.01, 2.00)
upper <- c(1200, 100, 5000, 5, 10, 50.0, 1.0, 6.00)

names(lower) <- names
names(upper) <- names

# Avoid exact zero values at lower bounds when the optimizer reaches a boundary.
eps <- 1e-6
lower[lower == 0] <- eps
```

8.5 Wrapper R function implementing CemaNeige-GR6J for hydroPSO

For the calibration of `CemaNeige-GR6J`, or any other hydrological model implemented as an R function, an R wrapper function must be created to connect the model with `hydroPSO`. This wrapper evaluates a candidate parameter set, runs the hydrological model, computes the objective function, and returns the information required by `hydroPSO` to guide the swarm through the parameter space. **This function MUST fulfil the following requirements:**

- 1) Its first argument must be named `param.values`, representing the numeric values of the parameters to be optimised.
- 2) One of its arguments must be named `obs`, representing the observed values used to evaluate the simulated streamflow generated by the hydrological model.
- 3) It must return a list object with, at least, the following elements:
 - 3.1) **GoF**: the goodness-of-fit value obtained when the hydrological model is run with `param.values` as the parameter set.
 - 3.2) **sim**: the model output obtained when the hydrological model is run with `param.values` as the parameter set. It MUST have the same object class and dimensions as the observed values provided by the user in `obs`.

This wrapper-function design is one of the main reasons why `hydroPSO` is useful beyond a single model. Once the interface is defined, the same optimisation engine can be applied to other hydrological models, objective functions, transformations, or calibration periods with limited changes to the surrounding workflow.

8.5.1 Required variables

`airGR` does not use `zoo` objects as model inputs; it works with plain numeric vectors and explicit date information. Therefore, the input time series must be transformed into numeric objects before running `CemaNeige-GR6J`:

```
P <- as.numeric(P.zoo)
Tmean <- as.numeric(Tmean.zoo)
PET <- as.numeric(PET.zoo)
Qobs <- as.numeric(Qobs.zoo)
```

Because `airGR` is a *suite* of hydrological models, running `CemaNeige-GR6J` requires a few preparatory objects that specify the selected model, input data, warm-up period, simulation period and snow elevation bands.

Before running `CemaNeige-GR6J`, at least the following variables must be defined:

- 1) **FUN_MOD**: R function defining the hydrological model to be executed (e.g. `RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J`, `RunModel_GR6J`, `RunModel_GR5J`).
- 2) **DatesR**: `POSIXt` object defining the dates corresponding to the precipitation, temperature and potential evapotranspiration time series used as **numeric** model inputs. Daily dates stored as `Date` objects can be transformed into `POSIXt` objects using the `as.POSIXt` function.
- 3) **InputsModel**: `InputsModel` object storing the daily precipitation, temperature, potential evapotranspiration, dates, hypsometric information and R-based function used to run the `CemaNeige-GR6J` hydrological model. For more information see `?CreateInputsModel`.
- 4) **IndPeriod_WarmUp**: numeric index identifying the portion of the input meteorological time series (see `?CreateInputsModel`) to be considered as *warm-up* period. For more information see `?CreateRunOptions`.
- 5) **IndPeriod_Run**: numeric index identifying the portion of the input meteorological time series (see `?CreateInputsModel`) to be used to run the model and return the output object. The output object

will have the same temporal extent as the period identified by `IndPeriod_Run`. For more information see `?CreateRunOptions`.

- 6) **RunOptions**: `RunOptions` object (a particular type of list), created with the `CreateRunOptions` function, containing all the data required to compute the model outputs (e.g., `IndPeriod_WarmUp`, `IndPeriod_Run`, `IniStates`).

```
# dates for the full time period (calibration + verification)
dates <- time(P.zoo)

# Numeric index with the position of the warm-up period and the calibration period wrt 'dates'
WarmUpPeriod.index <- seq( pmatch(Warmup.Ini.Cal, dates), pmatch(Warmup.Fin.Cal, dates) )
CalPeriod.index     <- seq( pmatch(Cal.Ini, dates), pmatch(Cal.Fin, dates) )

# Inputs required by the CemaNeige-GR6J model: P, PET, Tmean, dates,
modelInputs <- CreateInputsModel(FUN_MOD= RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J,
                                DatesR= as.POSIXlt(dates),
                                Precip= P,
                                PotEvap= PET,
                                TempMean= Tmean,
                                HypsoData= hypsometric.values,
                                NLayers= NLayers)

## Warning in CreateInputsModel(FUN_MOD = RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J, DatesR =
## as.POSIXlt(dates), : 'ZInputs' is missing: HypsoData[51] is used

## input series were successfully created on 5 elevation layers for use by CemaNeige
runOptions.CAL <- CreateRunOptions(FUN_MOD= RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J,
                                  InputsModel= modelInputs,
                                  IndPeriod_WarmUp= WarmUpPeriod.index,
                                  IndPeriod_Run= CalPeriod.index)

## Warning in CreateIniStates(FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD, InputsModel = InputsModel, :
## 'RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J' does not require 'IntStore'. Values set to NA

## Warning in CreateIniStates(FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD, InputsModel = InputsModel, :
## 'RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J' does not require 'GthrCemaNeigeLayers' and
## 'GlocmaxCemaNeigeLayers'. Values set to NA

## Warning in CreateRunOptions(FUN_MOD = RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J, InputsModel = modelInputs, : 'MeanAnSo

Qobs.zoo.cal <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
dates.cal <- time(Qobs.zoo.cal)
```

8.5.2 Minimal hydromodInR function

The package-level `hydromodInR()` function is used below for direct diagnostic runs. With the current interface, a single named numeric vector can be passed directly through `Particles`; `hydromodInR()` converts it internally to a one-row parameter set, injects it into `model.FUN.args` as `param.values`, and then calls the user-defined `CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR()` model function. The model function itself contains only the `CemaNeige-GR6J`-specific `airGR` call and the goodness-of-fit calculation.

```
CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR <- function(param.values,
                                     InputsModel,
                                     RunOptions,
                                     FUN_MOD,
                                     obs,
                                     dates = time(obs),
                                     gof.FUN = "KGE",
                                     gof.FUN.args = list(method = "2012")) {

  # Running the CemaNeige-GR6J model
  modeloutput <- RunModel(Param = param.values,
                          InputsModel = InputsModel,
                          RunOptions = RunOptions,
                          FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD
                          )

  # Getting the outputs simulated by the CemaNeige-GR6J model
  sim <- zoo(as.numeric(modeloutput$Qsim), dates)

  # Computing model's performance
  gof.args <- modifyList(gof.FUN.args, list(sim = sim, obs = obs))
  gof      <- do.call(gof.FUN, gof.args)

  # Creating the output of the R function
  out <- list(GoF = gof, sim = sim)

  return(out)
} # 'CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR' END
```

The arguments that remain fixed across all calibration-period model runs are stored in `model.FUN.args`. This list is passed unchanged to `hydroPSO()` later. In direct diagnostic calls, the candidate parameter vector is passed directly to `hydromodInR()` through `Particles`:

```
model.FUN.args <- list(InputsModel = modelInputs,
                      RunOptions = runOptions.CAL,
                      FUN_MOD = RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J,
                      obs = Qobs.zoo.cal,
                      dates = dates.cal,
                      gof.FUN = "KGE",
                      gof.FUN.args = list(method = "2012")
                    )
```

8.6 Running CemaNeige-GR6J

The `hydromodInR()` function can now be called directly for simple diagnostic runs before calibration. This keeps the preliminary model checks consistent with the same evaluation path that will later be used internally by `hydroPSO`.

8.6.1 Average parameter set

Before calibrating `CemaNeige-GR6J`, it is good practice to verify that the model runs correctly with the prepared input data. As a first diagnostic run, the parameter set is defined as the midpoint between the lower and upper bounds of each model parameter:

```
params <- lower + (upper - lower) / 2
modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = params,
                          model.FUN = CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR,
                          model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args)
```

The output returned by `hydromodInR()` includes the simulated streamflow and the goodness-of-fit value required by `hydroPSO`:

```
str(modeloutput)
```

```
## List of 2
## $ GoF: num 0.659
## $ sim:'zoo' series from 1980-01-01 to 1997-12-31
## Data: num [1:6575] 4.68 4.57 4.47 4.37 4.27 ...
## Index: Date[1:6575], format: "1980-01-01" "1980-01-02" ...
```

For this example, only simulated streamflow is extracted, because it is the model output that can be directly compared with the observed discharge series loaded above:

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- modeloutput$sim
Qsim <- as.numeric(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

The model outputs returned by `CemaNeige-GR6J` cover only the period defined by the `IndPeriod_Run` argument in `CreateRunOptions`, i.e., the period from `Cal.Ini` to `Cal.Fin`. Therefore, before comparing simulated streamflow with its observed counterpart, the observations (`Qobs`) must be subset to the same simulation period:

```
Qobs.zoo <- zoo(Qobs, dates)
Qobs.zoo.cal <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
```

The direct `hydromodInR()` call returns the simulated streamflow as a `zoo` object. The following object stores

the associated dates for consistency with the rest of the vignette:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

Graphical comparison between the **daily** observed and simulated time series obtained with the *average* parameter set:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ylab="Q, [mm]", lty=c(1, 1), cex=0.4)
```


Figure 2: Evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

This first diagnostic run is useful, but the low-flow behaviour can still be improved. The next step is to evaluate a parameter set included in Coron & Michel (2025).

8.6.2 (pseudo) *Default* parameter set

There is no single *default* parameter set for CemaNeige-GR6J (Coron & Michel, 2025). Therefore, as a second diagnostic run, this tutorial uses a parameter set provided in the example of the `CreateRunOptions` function in the manual of the `airGR` R package (Coron & Michel, 2025):

```
params <- c(X1 = 116.482, X2 = 0.500, X3 = 72.733, X4 = 1.224,  
           X5 = 0.278, X6 = 30.333, Ctg = 0.977, Kf = 2.776)  
names(params) <- names  
  
modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = params,  
                           model.FUN = CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR,  
                           model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args)
```

Extract only the simulated streamflow from the full model output:

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- modeloutput$sim  
Qsim <- as.numeric(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

The direct `hydromodInR()` call returns the simulated streamflow as a `zoo` object. The following object stores the associated dates for consistency with the rest of the vignette:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qsim.zoo.cal)
```

Graphical comparison between the **daily** observed and simulated time series obtained with this reference parameter set:

```
ggof( sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ylab="Q, [mm]", lty=c(1, 1), cex=0.4)
```


Figure 3: Evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

This parameter set improves the simulation relative to the previous diagnostic run, but there is still substantial room for improvement through formal calibration.

9 Calibrating CemaNeige-GR6J with hydroPSO

9.1 Subsetting for the calibration period

For the calibration of CemaNeige-GR6J with hydroPSO, only part of the available input time series is used. The remaining period is reserved for independent verification, which provides a more robust assessment of the calibrated parameter set:

```
P.zoo.cal      <- window(P.zoo      , start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
PET.zoo.cal    <- window(PET.zoo    , start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
Tmean.zoo.cal  <- window(Tmean.zoo  , start=Warmup.Ini.Cal, end=Cal.Fin)
```

Because the model outputs returned by CemaNeige-GR6J cover only the period defined by the `IndPeriod_Run` argument in `CreateRunOptions`, i.e., the time period from `Cal.Ini` to `Cal.Fin`, the observations (`Qobs`) must be subset to the same simulation period before they are compared with the simulated streamflows:

```
Qobs.zoo      <- zoo(Qobs, dates)
Qobs.zoo.cal  <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Cal.Ini, end=Cal.Fin)
```

Store the dates associated with the period used to evaluate the calibration outputs:

```
dates.cal <- time(Qobs.zoo.cal)
```

9.2 Running the calibration

The CemaNeige-GR6J model can now be calibrated with hydroPSO using `fn = "hydromodInR"` and the `model.FUN.args` list defined above:

```
out <- hydroPSO(fn = "hydromodInR",
               lower = lower, upper = upper, method = "sps2011",
               control = list(drty.out = PSO.drty.out, write2disk = TRUE,
                             MinMax = "max", npart = 80, maxit = 50,
                             normalise = TRUE, REPORT = 10,
                             parallel = "none", reltol = 1E-10),
               model.FUN = CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR,
               model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args
               )
```

In the previous code chunk, the arguments passed to `hydroPSO` are briefly explained below (more information can be found with `?hydroPSO`):

- a) **fn**: character string used to tell `hydroPSO` that it will optimise an R-based hydrological model.
- b) **lower**: numeric vector defining the lower boundaries of the model parameters.
- c) **upper**: numeric vector defining the upper boundaries of the model parameters.
- d) **method**: character string defining the PSO algorithm used to calibrate the hydrological model.
- e) **model.FUN**: R function used to run the hydrological model, returning model simulations and their corresponding goodness-of-fit value while fulfilling the three requirements mentioned in Section 9.2.
- f) **model.FUN.args**: list object containing all arguments used to run the hydrological model, in addition to **param.values**.
- g) **control**: list object containing the arguments used to fine-tune the calibration with `hydroPSO`. The arguments passed to `control` affect how `hydroPSO` explores the parameter space and how optimisation outputs are written. Particular attention should be given to the following:
 - *drty.out*: character, with the full path to directory that will store the output files of `hydroPSO`, only used when `write2disk=FALSE`. By default `drty.out="PSO.out"` which is looked for within the

current working directory. If `drty.out` does not exist, it is automatically created by `hydroPSO` with an informative warning message.

- `write2disk`: logical, indicates whether the output files will be written to the disk or not. By default `write2disk=TRUE`. If you are only interested in the *optimum* parameter set found by `hydroPSO` and the corresponding simulated values obtained when running `SWAT+` with that parameter set, you should set `write2disk=FALSE`, to reduce the storage used in your computer and to reduce the total computation time (because internal files are not written to disk). However, if you set `write2disk=FALSE` you will not be able to use the `plot_results` function, because it requires the internal files created by `hydroPSO` when `write2disk=TRUE`.
- `MinMax`: character string indicating whether the calibration solves a maximisation or minimisation problem. Valid values are `c('min', 'max')`. The default value is `"min"`.
- `npart`: numeric value defining the number of particles in the swarm. By default, `npart=NA`, which means that the swarm size depends on the selected method: `npart=ceiling(10+2*sqrt(n))2` when `method='sps02007'`, or `npart=40` otherwise.
- `maxit`: numeric, maximum number of iterations. By default `maxit=1000`.
- `Xini.type`: character, indicates how to initialise the particles' positions in the swarm within the ranges defined by `lower` and `upper`. By default `Xini.type='random'` (random initialisation of positions). However, you might want to try `Xini.type='lhs'` (Latin Hypercube initialisation), or `Xini.type='sobol'` (since `hydroPSO>=0.6`, for quasi-random initialisation of particle's positions using uniform Sobol low discrepancy numbers).
- `boundary.wall`: sometimes PSO fails to keep particles within the valid search space. This argument addresses this by defining exactly how out-of-bounds particles are managed. The specific values it can take are:
 - `NA`: The default setting. It automatically applies either `absorbing2007` or `absorbing2011` depending on the chosen optimisation method.
 - `absorbing2011`: Clamps the particle's position to the boundary edge but flexibly modifies its velocity, allowing it to smoothly 'slide' along the wall rather than stopping completely.
 - `absorbing2007`: A strict clamp that locks the particle to the edge and zeroes its velocity. The particle remains stuck without momentum until algorithmic forces pull it back inside.
 - `reflecting`: Acts as a perfectly elastic surface. It mirrors the particle back inside and exactly reverses its velocity, preserving kinetic energy for continuous, aggressive exploration.
 - `damping`: Functions as an inelastic collision. It reflects the particle back into the space but applies a random reduction to its reversed velocity to bleed off kinetic energy and prevent endless oscillation.
 - `invisible`: Mathematically ignores the boundaries, allowing particles to fly freely outside without altering position or velocity. Out-of-bounds fitness is not evaluated; the particle relies on the attraction of its historical bests to eventually return.
- `normalise`: logical, indicates whether the parameter values have to be normalised to the `[0,1]` interval during the optimisation or not. It is recommended to use this option when the search space is not an hypercube. By default `normalise=FALSE`.
- `reltol`: numeric, relative convergence tolerance. By default `reltol=sqrt(.Machine$double.eps)`, typically, about `1e-8`.
- `REPORT`: numeric, indicates the frequency of report messages printed to the screen. Default to every 100 iterations. Only used when `verbose=TRUE`.
- `parallel`: character, indicates how to parallelise `hydroPSO`. By default `parallel="none"`. Other possible values are: `parallel="parallel"` (for unix-alike machines) and `parallel="parallelWin"` (for MS Windows machines).

²`n` is the number of model parameters being calibrated.

- *par.nnodes*: numeric, indicates the number of cores/CPU's to be used in the local multi-core machine, or the number of nodes to be used in the network cluster. By default `par.nnodes=NA`, which assigns `par.nnodes=parallel::detectCores()` only when `parallel!="none"`.
- *par.pkgs*: list of package names (as characters) that need to be loaded on each node for allowing the objective function `fn` to be evaluated. By default `par.pkgs=list()`. Used only when `parallel="parallelWin"`.

The maximum number of model evaluations during calibration is approximately `npart * maxit`, and the **total execution time** depends on both the cost of one model run and the number of evaluations required by the optimisation. This makes the choice of swarm size (`npart`) and the maximum number of iterations (`maxit`) a practical compromise between search robustness and computational cost.

Using `npart=40` should be good enough for most model applications. However, if the number of parameters of your model is ~ 10 or more, I suggest to **explore the use of a larger number of particles in combination with a lower number of model runs** (e.g., `npart=80` and `maxit=50`). The latter ensures that `hydroPSO` will have enough number of particles to effectively tackle the *curse of dimensionality*, and help to reduce premature convergence, which is particularly relevant for hydrological models affected by parameter interactions, threshold behaviour, and equifinality.

9.3 Basic analysis of calibration results

The best parameter set obtained during calibration and its corresponding goodness-of-fit value can be inspected as follows:

```
# 'best' parameter set obtained during calibration
out$par
```

```
##           X1           X2           X3           X4           X5           X6
## 135.6632044  7.5469786 956.3216490  3.5378224  0.3329169 40.1877042
##           Ctg           Kf
##  0.3733393  5.2259020
```

```
# goodness-of-fit obtained for the 'best' parameter set
out$value
```

```
## [1] 0.833314
```

Saving the *best* parameter set obtained during the calibration:

```
best.param.cal <- out$par
```

The variables required to run CemaNeige-GR6J were defined earlier (i.e., InputsModel and RunOptions). The model can now be run with the *best* parameter set obtained during calibration:

```
modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = best.param.cal,
                           model.FUN = CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR,
                           model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args)
```

Extract the simulated streamflow returned by hydromodInR():

```
Qsim.zoo.cal <- modeloutput$sim
```

Defining a customised title for all the following figures:

```
main <- paste0("CN-GR6J: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
```

The following plot **compares daily observed streamflow with the simulation** obtained using the best parameter set for the calibration period, excluding the warm-up period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.3, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 4: Graphical comparison of streamflows simulated by CemaNeige-GR6J during the calibration period using several performance indices.

The calibrated simulation provides a substantial improvement over the preliminary diagnostic runs and illustrates the value of formal parameter optimisation.

Graphical comparison of **daily** and **monthly** simulated ($Q_{sim.zoo.cal}$) and observed ($Q_{obs.zoo.cal}$) values for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="dm",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 5: Daily and monthly evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison of **monthly and annual** simulated and observed values for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="ma", pt.style="bar",
     FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 6: Monthly and annual evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison of **seasonal** simulated and observed values (one plot for each season) for the calibration period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.cal, obs=Qobs.zoo.cal, ftype="seasonal", ylab="Q, [mm]",
     season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
     FUN=mean, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 7: Seasonal evaluation of simulated streamflows for the calibration period using several performance indices.

Computing the **daily residuals** for the calibration period:

```
residuals <- Qsim.zoo.cal - Qobs.zoo.cal
```

Plotting **daily, monthly and annual time series, boxplots and histograms** of the residuals for the calibration period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, var.unit="mm")
```


Figure 8: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the calibration period at the daily, monthly, and annual temporal scales.

Seasonal time series and boxplots of the residuals for the calibration period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, pfreq="seasonal",
season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
h=0, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 9: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the calibration period at the seasonal scale.

9.4 Plotting calibration results

Customised title for all the figures in this section:

```
main <- paste0("CN-GR6J: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
```

9.4.1 Basic plotting

The `plot_results` function included in `hydroPSO` automatically generates diagnostic figures that support the evaluation of the calibration process and the interpretation of parameter behaviour. Internally, it calls `read_results` and produces the following eleven figures:

- 1) Dotty plots of parameter values.
- 2) Histograms of parameter values.
- 3) Boxplots of parameter values.
- 4) Correlation matrix among parameter values (optional).
- 5) Empirical CDFs of parameter values.
- 6) Parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations.
- 7) (pseudo) 3D dotty plots of (selected) parameter values.
- 8) GoF for each particle against Number of Model Evaluations.
- 9) Velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations.
- 10a) Scatterplot between Best Simulated values and Observations (OPTIONAL, only if `MinMax` is provided).
- 10b) Empirical CDFs for model's output (only produced if `obs` is NOT a zoo object).
- 10b) ggof (See `?ggof`) between Best Simulated values and Observations (OPTIONAL, only if `obs` is a zoo object).
- 10d) Empirical CDFs for selected quantiles of model's output (OPTIONAL, only if `obs` is a zoo object).
- 11) Convergence Measures (`Gbest` and `normSwarmRadius`) vs Iteration Number.

You can try the basic automatic plotting of the calibration results into the current graphic device (usually, your screen) with:

```
plot_results()
```

9.4.2 Advanced plotting

Notwithstanding the automatic plotting of the calibration results might be good enough for most purposes, you should read `?plot_results` and customise some of its arguments for getting figures that fulfill your case-specific needs:

```
plot_results(drty.out=PSO.drty.out, # directory that stores all the calibration outputs
            do.png=TRUE,           # plots go to PNG figures instead of to the screen
            params.png.width=630,  # 7 inches equals 630 pixels at 90 DPI. 900
            params.png.height=855, # 9.5 inches equals 855 pixels at 90 DPI. 1500
            MinMax="max",          # 'best' parameter set is the one with the highest GoF
            beh.thr=0.3,           # behavioural parameter sets (with GoF >= 0.3 )
            ftype="dm",            # to produce daily and monthly figures of 'sim' vs 'obs'
            nrows=5,               # number of rows in parameter figures (histograms,...)
            FUN=mean,              # function used to compute monthly values
            do.pairs=TRUE,         # correlation plot among parameters and GoF
            gof.name="KGE2012",    # name used for axis titles in parameter figures
            legend.pos="right",    # position of the legend in the convergence plot
            main=main              # user-defined title for most of the output figures
        )
```

```
## [                               ]
## [      Reading output files ... ]
## [                               ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 664 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 664 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6575 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs           : 664 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 50 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 48 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 80 ]
```

```

## [ Number of iterations: 50 ]
## [                               ]
## [           Plotting ...       ]
## [                               ]
## [ Plotting convergence measures into 'ConvergenceMeasures.png' ... ]
##
## [ Plotting dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_DottyPlots.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting histograms for parameter values into 'Params_Histograms.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting boxplots for parameter values into 'Params_Boxplots.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting correlation matrix for parameter values into 'Params_Pairs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting empirical CDFs for parameter values into 'Params_ECDFs.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting parameter values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Params_ValuesPerRun.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting 3D dotty plots for parameter values into 'Params_dp3d.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting GoF for each particle vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Particles_GofPerIter.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting velocity values vs Number of Model Evaluations into 'Velocities_ValuePerRun.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-Corr.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting best simulated values vs observations into 'ModelOut_BestSim_vs_Obs-ggof.png' ... ]
## [ Plotting ECDFs of simulated quantiles vs observations into 'ModelOut_Quantiles.png' ... ]
## [ Computing un-weighted quantiles for each ROW of 'sim' ... ]
## |                               |

```

All the figures generated by the previous call to `plot_results` are **not discussed in this tutorial**, but you can read some discussions about them on Rojas & Zambrano-Bigiarini (2012), Zambrano-Bigiarini & Rojas (2013), Abdelaziz & Zambrano-Bigiarini (2014) and Abdelaziz et al. (2019).

9.4.2.1 Convergence along iterations

This figure shows the change in the **objective function** (black line) and the change in the **normalised swarm radius** (a measure of swarm spread on the search space) along with the number of iterations used in the optimisation. This figure can be used to obtain a founded guess about the minimum number of iterations required to obtain a satisfactory value of the objective function.

Figure 10: Evolution of global optimum (i.e., KGE2012) and the normalized swarm radius against the number of iterations.

9.4.2.2 Histograms

This figure shows **histograms** of parameter values considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

CN-GR6J: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 11: Histograms of parameter values for user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.4.2.3 Boxplots

This figure shows **boxplots** of parameter values considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation.

CN-GR6J: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 12: Box-and-whisker plots (or boxplots) of parameter values for user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The horizontal red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.4.2.4 Dotty plots

This figure shows **dotty plots** of parameter values versus the objective function, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum value obtained for each parameter during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance.

CN-GR6J: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 13: Dotty plots showing the model performance of behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh.thr}$). The vertical red line indicates the optimum parameter value found during the optimisation, whereas the horizontal red line shows the corresponding best model performance. Parameter names are described in Table 1.

9.4.2.5 Empirical CDFs

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** of parameter values, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets (KGE2012 \geq beh.thr). Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (median of the distribution). Vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5 (its value is shown in the upper part of each figure).

CN-GR6J: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 14: Empirical CDFs (continuous black lines) of parameter values. Horizontal grey dotted lines represent a cumulative probability equal to 0.5, and vertical grey dotted lines represent the parameter value corresponding to a cumulative probability equal to 0.5.

9.4.2.6 3D dotted plots

This figure shows a scatter-based diagnostic plot (aka **pseudo three-dimensional dotted plots**) to explore the relationship between pairs of model parameters and a goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric, considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE_{2012} \geq \text{beh. thr}$). Regions with blue (red) colours illustrate parameter ranges where the interaction of two parameters lead to high (low) model performance. This function is particularly useful in hydrological modelling to assess parameter interactions, equifinality, and behavioural regions after calibration or Monte Carlo simulation.

Figure 15: Three-dimensional dotted plots to explore the relationship between pairs of model parameters and the goodness-of-fit (GOF) metric.

9.4.2.7 Correlation matrix

This figure shows **correlation matrix** between parameters and model performance (KGE2012), considering only user-defined behavioural parameter sets ($KGE2012 \geq \text{beh. thr}$). Horizontal and vertical axes show the physical range used for the calibration of each parameter. Red curved lines represents are fitted to all the pair of points using a lowess smoother, i.e., a locally-weighted polynomial regression.

CN-GR6J: Rio Trancura antes de Llafenco (9414001)

Figure 16: Correlation matrix between parameters and model performance (KGE2012). Horizontal and vertical axes show the physical range used for the calibration of each parameter. Red curved lines represents are fitted to all the pair of points using a lowess smoother.

9.4.2.8 Daily and monthly evaluation

This figure shows a **comparison of daily** (upper panel) and **monthly** (lower panel) **streamflows**, obtained with the *best* parameter set obtained during the optimisation, against their corresponding observed counterparts.

Figure 17: Comparison of daily (upper panel) and monthly (lower panel) streamflows obtained with the 'best' parameter set against their corresponding observed counterparts.

9.4.2.9 Scatterplot of daily values

This figure shows a **Scatterplot** comparing observed streamflows against the simulated values obtained with the *best* parameter set obtained during the optimisation.

Figure 18: Scatterplot of daily streamflows obtained with the 'best' parameter set obtained during calibration and their corresponding observed counterparts.

9.4.2.10 Evaluation of low, medium and high streamflows

This figure shows **empirical CDFs** (blue lines) for 5, 50 and 95 quantiles of simulated discharges obtained by **CemaNeige-GR6J** during the calibration period. The previous quantiles were selected as representative of low, medium and high streamflows, respectively. Vertical black-dotted lines represent the observed 5, 50 and 95 quantiles, while vertical grey-dotted lines indicate the median of the simulated quantiles. Therefore, this figure is useful to assess the bias of model results in the low, medium and high part of the simulated time series.

Figure 19: Empirical CDFs (blue lines) for 5, 50 and 95 quantiles of simulated discharges obtained by CemaNeige-GR6J during the calibration period. Vertical black-dotted lines represent the observed quantiles, while vertical grey-dotted lines indicate the median of the simulated quantiles.

9.5 Uncertainty analysis of calibration results

If you are not familiar with uncertainty analysis, you might be interested in Refsgaard et al. (2007), who review the terminology and typology of uncertainty, its interaction with the broader water management process and the role of uncertainty at different stages in the modelling processes.

9.5.1 Reading all calibration results

In order to proceed with the uncertainty analysis, we need to read all the calibration results generated by hydroPSO during the optimisation. However, for this tutorial we are only interested in **behavioural parameter sets** (Beven, 2006; Beven & Binley, 1992; Beven & Freer, 2001), as defined by an arbitrary and user-defined goodness-of-fit value (i.e., a KGE2012 value). For this particular case, we choose `beh.thr=0.3`. Setting `beh.thr=0.3` and `MinMax='max'` will consider as behavioural all those parameter sets with goodness-of-fit values higher than the user-defined threshold 0.3:

```
res <- read_results(drty.out=PSO.drty.out, MinMax="max", beh.thr=0.3)

## [ ]
## [ Reading output files ... ]
## [ ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 664 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Velocities.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of behavioural parameter sets: 664 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Model_out.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of parameter sets: 4000 ]
## [ Number of model outputs for each parameter set ('nsim'): 6575 ]
## [ Number of behavioural model outputs : 664 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'ConvergenceMeasures.txt' ... ]
## [ Total number of iterations: 50 ]
## [ Number of iterations with Gbest >= 0.3: 48 ]
##
## [ Reading the file 'Particles_GofPerIter.txt' ... ]
## [ Number of particles : 80 ]
## [ Number of iterations: 50 ]
```

The next code chunk assigns all the behavioural parameter sets obtained during calibration (*params*), i.e., those with goodness-of-fit value higher than `beh.thr`; the goodness-of-fit value of each behavioural parameter set (*gofs*), the model outputs (i.e., streamflows for the *CemaNeige-GR6J* case) corresponding to each behavioural parameter set (*Qsims*), the model output corresponding to the best parameter set obtained during calibration (*model.best*), and the observed values used in the calibration to compute the goodness-of-fit value (*model.obs*):

```
params    <- res[["params"]]
gofs     <- res[["gofs"]]
Qsims    <- res[["model.values"]]
model.best <- res[["model.best"]]
model.obs <- res[["model.obs"]]
```

9.5.2 Weighted quantiles of parameter values

The computation of weighted quantiles of model parameters would provide an estimate of the uncertainty in each model parameter, based on the behavioural parameter sets obtained during calibration and the goodness-of-fit values obtained for each one of them.

User-defined weighted quantiles for each model parameter are obtained multiplying the standard quantile derived for each model parameter based on all the behavioural parameter sets (i.e., for each column in `params`) by the corresponding goodness-of-fit value obtained by the parameter set (*gofs*)³.

For this tutorial, we use the `wquantile` function of `hydroPSO` to compute the 2.5, 50 and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each model parameter, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
params.025.50.975 <- wquantile(params, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE,
                              probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
                              normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
```

You might be interested in how far are the best parameter set found during the calibration from the median of the weighted behavioural parameter sets. In the following code chunk we will add a new column to `params.025.50.975`, just after the median (quantile 50):

```
params.025.50.best.975 <- cbind(params.025.50.975[, c(1,2)],
                                Best=as.numeric(best.param.cal),
                                params.025.50.975[, 3]
                                )
colnames(params.025.50.best.975)[4] <- "97.5%"
round( params.025.50.best.975, 2)
```

FALSE	2.5%	50%	Best	97.5%
FALSE X1	80.00	312.66	135.66	901.93
FALSE X2	-10.12	0.47	7.55	9.37
FALSE X3	750.19	1631.01	956.32	4022.89
FALSE X4	0.65	3.33	3.54	4.62
FALSE X5	-1.36	0.31	0.33	1.68
FALSE X6	5.75	40.52	40.19	49.24
FALSE Ctg	0.13	0.35	0.37	0.83
FALSE Kf	2.63	4.20	5.23	5.63

9.5.3 Weighted quantiles of model simulations

The computation of weighted quantiles of model simulations would provide an estimate of the uncertainty in each model simulated value (i.e., each daily streamflow), based on the goodness-of-fit values obtained for the

³For more information about the computation of the weighted quantiles, please read `?wtd.stats`.

full time series simulated by the model.

User-defined weighted quantiles for each model simulation are obtained multiplying the standard quantile derived for each model simulation based on all the model simulations (i.e., for each column in `Qsims`) by the corresponding goodness-of-fit value obtained by the full time series simulated by the model (`gofs`).

For this tutorial, we use the `wquantile` function of `hydroPS0` to compute the 2.5, 50 and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each value simulated by the model, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
Qsim.025.q50.q975 <- wquantile(Qsims, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
                              normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
round( head(Qsim.025.q50.q975), 3)
```

```
FALSE      2.5%   50% 97.5%
FALSE Sim1 3.066 5.095 8.591
FALSE Sim2 2.963 4.977 8.445
FALSE Sim3 2.855 4.869 8.298
FALSE Sim4 2.758 4.762 8.162
FALSE Sim5 2.668 4.666 8.021
FALSE Sim6 2.582 4.574 7.893
```

To plot the uncertainty bounds for each model simulated value, we are going to transform the weighted quantiles 2.5 and 97.5 into zoo objects:

```
dates.cal <- hydroTSM::dip(Cal.Ini, Cal.Fin)
q025      <- zoo::zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,1], dates.cal)
q975      <- zoo::zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,3], dates.cal)
```

9.5.4 P-factor and R-factor

The **P-factor** is then computed (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the percent of observations that are within the user-defined uncertainty bounds:

```
( pf <- pfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
```

```
## [1] 0.9469202
```

The **R-factor** is also computed (Abbaspour et al., 2009; Schuol et al., 2008), which represents the average width of the user-defined uncertainty bounds divided by the standard deviation of the observations:

```
( rf <- rfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
```

```
## [1] 1.29807
```

A useful uncertainty envelope should bracket a large fraction of the observations (high P-factor, with a maximum of 1) while remaining as narrow as possible (low R-factor, with a minimum of 0).

9.5.5 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)

The following plot shows the *best* simulated streamflows along with the **95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)** (Abbaspour et al., 2007, 2009; Schuol et al., 2008):

```

main.uncert <- paste0("Uncertainty bounds CemaNeige-GR6J: ",
                      Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
Qobs.col <- "black"
best.sim.col <- "blue"
bands.col <- "lightblue"

Qsim.best.zoo <- zoo::zoo(model.best, time(Qobs.zoo.cal) )

plot(Qobs.zoo.cal, xaxt="n", xlab="", type="n", main=main.uncert, ylab="Q, [mm]") # empty plotting area
drawTimeAxis(Qobs.zoo.cal) # time axis
plotbandsonly(lband=q025, uband=q975) # 95 PPU
lines(Qobs.zoo.cal, col=Qobs.col, lwd=0.3) # Qobs
lines(Qsim.best.zoo, col=best.sim.col, lwd=0.3) # best simulation
grid()

legend("topright", legend=c("Qobs", "best.sim", "95PPU"), lty=c(1, 1, NA),
      pch=c(NA, NA, 15), col=c(Qobs.col, best.sim.col, bands.col),
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)

legend("topleft", legend=c(paste0("P-factor: ", round(pf, 2)),
      paste0("R-factor: ", round(rf, 2)) ),
      bty="n", cex = 1.2)

```


Figure 20: 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU) for model simulations during the calibration period.

9.5.6 Uncertainty in flow duration curve

The `fdcu` function from `hydroTSM` is used to plot the observed flow duration curve (FDC), the one of the *best* simulated streamflows, and the flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the calibration period:

```
main.uncert <- paste0("FDC CemaNeige-GR6J model: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")" )
bands.col   <- "lightskyblue1"

par(mfrow=c(3, 1), mar = c(2, 3.5, 1, 1), oma=c(0, 0, 0, 0), mgp=c(2, 0.75, 0) )
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo, bands.col=bands.col,
     main="", log="y") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.cal, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.best.zoo, bands.col=bands.col,
     main="", log="x") # empty plotting area
grid()
```


Figure 21: Flow duration curve of the observed (black line) and best simulated (blue line) streamflows. In addition, flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the calibration period. The upper panel is the normal flow duration curve, the middle panel has focus on low flows ($\log='y'$) and the lower panel has focus on high flows ($\log='x'$).

9.5.7 Some comments about P-factor and R-factor

GLUE-like uncertainty analysis (Beven, 2006; Beven et al., 2008; Beven & Binley, 1992) is sensitive to the threshold used to define behavioural parameter sets (`beh.thr`). Lower thresholds usually retain more parameter sets and therefore produce wider posterior ranges for parameters and model simulations (Jin et al., 2010). This can increase the fraction of observations bracketed by the uncertainty band, but it may also reduce the sharpness and practical usefulness of the predictive interval.

In general, decreasing `beh.thr` tends to increase the P-factor, but this improvement is usually obtained at the expense of a larger R-factor. The two indicators should therefore be interpreted together: a high P-factor is desirable only when the associated uncertainty band remains sufficiently narrow for the intended hydrological application.

10 Verification analysis

10.1 Basic analysis of the verification period

To proceed with the verification analysis, the temporal extent of the verification period must first be defined (i.e., from `Ver.Ini` to `Ver.Fin`) and the corresponding warmup period. Because the full meteorological record spans 1979-2016 and the verification period starts in 1999, the period from 1979-01-01 to 1998-12-31 is used as warm-up for the verification run:

```
# dates corresponding to the verification period,
dates.ver <- dip(Ver.Ini, Ver.Fin)

# Numeric index with the position of the warm-up period and the calibration period wrt 'dates'
WarmUpPeriod.index <- seq( pmatch(Warmup.Ini.Cal, dates), pmatch(Warmup.Fin.Ver, dates) )
VerPeriod.index      <- seq( pmatch(Ver.Ini, dates), pmatch(Ver.Fin, dates) )

# Inputs required by the CemaNeige-GR6J model: P, PET, Tmean, dates
modelInputs <- CreateInputsModel(FUN_MOD= RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J,
                                DatesR= as.POSIXlt(dates),
                                Precip= P,
                                PotEvap= PET,
                                TempMean= Tmean,
                                HypsoData= hypsometric.values,
                                NLayers= NLayers)

## Warning in CreateInputsModel(FUN_MOD = RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J, DatesR =
## as.POSIXlt(dates), : 'ZInputs' is missing: HypsoData[51] is used

## input series were successfully created on 5 elevation layers for use by CemaNeige

runOptions.VER <- CreateRunOptions(FUN_MOD= RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J,
                                  InputsModel= modelInputs,
                                  IndPeriod_WarmUp= WarmUpPeriod.index,
                                  IndPeriod_Run= VerPeriod.index)

## Warning in CreateIniStates(FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD, InputsModel = InputsModel, :
## 'RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J' does not require 'IntStore'. Values set to NA

## Warning in CreateIniStates(FUN_MOD = FUN_MOD, InputsModel = InputsModel, :
## 'RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J' does not require 'GthrCemaNeigeLayers' and
## 'GlocmaxCemaNeigeLayers'. Values set to NA

## Warning in CreateRunOptions(FUN_MOD = RunModel_CemaNeigeGR6J, InputsModel = modelInputs, : 'MeanAnSo
```

```

Qobs.zoo.ver <- window(Qobs.zoo, start=Ver.Ini, end=Ver.Fin)

model.FUN.args.ver <- modifyList(
  model.FUN.args,
  list(
    InputsModel = modelInputs,
    RunOptions = runOptions.VER,
    obs = Qobs.zoo.ver,
    dates = dates.ver
  )
)

```

Run CemaNeige-GR6J with the *best* parameter set obtained during calibration for the verification period, using the same direct `hydromodInR()` setup and the verification-specific `model.FUN.args.ver` list:

```

modeloutput <- hydromodInR(param.values = best.param.cal,
  model.FUN = CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR,
  model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args.ver)

```

Extract the simulated streamflow returned by `hydromodInR()`:

```
Qsim.zoo <- modeloutput$sim
```

The model outputs returned by CemaNeige-GR6J cover only the period defined by the `IndPeriod_Run` argument in `CreateRunOptions`, i.e., the time period from `Ver.Ini` to `Ver.Fin`. Therefore, before comparing simulated streamflow with its observed counterpart, the observations (`Qobs`) must be subset to the same verification period:

```
Qsim.zoo.ver <- Qsim.zoo # just for using the same variable names afterwards
```

Graphical comparison between the daily observed and simulated time series obtained with the *best* parameter set for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.3, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 22: Graphical comparison of daily observed and simulated streamflow time series obtained with the **best** parameter set obtained during the calibration.

The verification performance can now be assessed against an independent period, rather than inferred from the calibration results.

Graphical comparison between **daily** and **monthly** simulated ($Q_{sim.zoo.ver}$) and observed ($Q_{obs.zoo.ver}$) values for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="dm",
FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 23: Daily and monthly evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison of **monthly** and **annual** simulated and observed values for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="ma", pt.style="bar",
FUN=mean, main=main, ylab="Q, [mm]", cex=0.4, lty=c(1,1) )
```


Figure 24: Monthly and annual evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Graphical comparison of **seasonal** simulated and observed values (one plot for each season) for the verification period:

```
ggof(sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, obs=Qobs.zoo.ver, ftype="seasonal", ylab="Q, [mm]",
    season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
    FUN=mean, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 25: Seasonal evaluation of simulated streamflows for the verification period using several performance indices.

Computing the **daily residuals** for the verification period:

```
residuals <- Qsim.zoo.ver - Qobs.zoo.ver  
residuals <- window(residuals, start=Ver.Ini)
```

Plot daily, monthly, and annual time series, boxplots, and histograms of the **residuals for the verification** period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, var.unit="mm")
```


Figure 26: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the verification period at the daily, monthly, and annual temporal scales.

Seasonal time series and boxplots of the residuals for the verification period:

```
hydroplot(residuals, FUN=mean, pfreq="seasonal",
season.names=c("Summer", "Autumn", "Winter", "Spring"),
h=0, main=main, cex.main=2)
```


Figure 27: Analysis of the residuals (simulations - observations) for the verification period at the seasonal scale.

10.2 Running behavioural parameter sets

One advantage of the CemaNeige-GR6J implementation in airGR is that model inputs and run options can be redefined for the independent verification period without changing the model function. The object `model.FUN.args.ver`, defined above, updates the period-specific elements of `model.FUN.args` and is reused by `verification()`.

Since hydroPSO v0.5-0, the `verification` function is fully compatible with R-based hydrological and environmental models. It can therefore be used to **run the model with all behavioural parameter sets** obtained during calibration. This makes it possible to obtain the full time series of simulated values associated with each behavioural parameter set during the verification period, which is essential for uncertainty analysis and robustness assessment:

```
out <- verification(fn = "hydromodInR",
  par = params,
  control = list(gof.name = "KGE2012", # Only used for plot titles
    MinMax = "max", # Are we looking for a minimum or maximum?
    do.plots = FALSE,
    write2disk = TRUE,
    parallel = "none",
    verbose = TRUE),
  model.FUN = CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR,
  model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args.ver
)
```

In the previous code chunk, the arguments passed to `verification` have the same meaning as those of `hydroPSO` (more information can be found with `?verification`), with the exception of:

-) `par`: `data.frame` with all the parameter sets that will be run with CemaNeige-GR6J. In this case, `params` was already read using a behavioural threshold equal to `beh.thr`.

10.3 Uncertainty analysis of verification results

10.3.1 Reading all verification results

To perform the verification uncertainty analysis, all simulations generated by the previous call to `verification` are first read from disk:

```
gofs <- out[["gofs"]]
Qsims <- out[["model.values"]]
best.param.ver <- out[["best.param"]]
best.gof <- out[["best.gof"]]
```

10.3.2 Weighted quantiles of model simulations

The computation of weighted quantiles of model simulations provides an estimate of predictive uncertainty for each simulated value, using the goodness-of-fit values obtained during verification as weights. User-defined weighted quantiles for each simulation time step are computed from the ensemble of verification simulations, using the goodness-of-fit values of the complete simulated time series as weights. For this tutorial, we use the `wquantile` function of `hydroPSO` to compute the 2.5, 50 and 97.5 weighted quantiles for each value simulated by the model, by setting `probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975)`:

```
Qsim.025.q50.q975 <- wquantile(Qsims, weights=gofs, byrow=FALSE, probs=c(0.025, 0.5, 0.975),
  normwt=TRUE, verbose=FALSE)
round( head(Qsim.025.q50.q975), 3)
```

```

FALSE      2.5%   50% 97.5%
FALSE sim1 0.259 1.527 5.206
FALSE sim2 0.253 1.509 5.167
FALSE sim3 0.247 1.492 5.148
FALSE sim4 0.241 1.481 5.136
FALSE sim5 0.236 1.470 5.122
FALSE sim6 0.231 1.454 5.108

```

To plot the uncertainty bounds for each value simulated during the verification period, we are going to transform the weighted quantiles 2.5 and 97.5 into zoo objects:

```

dates.ver <- dip(Ver.Ini, Ver.Fin)
q025      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,1], dates.ver)
q975      <- zoo(Qsim.025.q50.q975[,3], dates.ver)

```

10.3.3 P-factor and R-factor

The **P-factor** is then computed ([Abbaspour et al., 2009](#); [Schuol et al., 2008](#)), which represents the percent of observations that are within the user-defined uncertainty bounds:

```

( pf <- pfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
## [1] 0.9092015

```

The **R-factor** is also computed ([Abbaspour et al., 2009](#); [Schuol et al., 2008](#)), which represents the average width of the user-defined uncertainty bounds divided by the standard deviation of the observations:

```

( rf <- rfactor(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, na.rm=TRUE) )
## [1] 1.229826

```

A useful uncertainty envelope should bracket a large fraction of the observations (high P-factor, with a maximum of 1) while remaining as narrow as possible (low R-factor, with a minimum of 0).

10.3.4 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)

The following plot shows the *best* simulated streamflows obtained during the verification along with the **95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU)** (Abbaspour et al., 2007, 2009; Schulz et al., 2008):

```

main.uncert <- paste0("Uncertainty bounds CemaNeige-GR6J: ",
  Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")")
Qobs.col <- "black"
best.sim.col <- "blue"
bands.col <- "lightblue"

plot(Qobs.zoo.ver, xaxt="n", xlab="", type="n", main=main.uncert, ylab="Q, [mm]") # empty plotting area
drawTimeAxis(Qobs.zoo.ver) # time axis
plotbandsonly(lband=q025, uband=q975) # 95 PPU
lines(Qobs.zoo.ver, col=Qobs.col, lwd=0.3) # Qobs
lines(Qsim.zoo.ver, col=best.sim.col, lwd=0.3) # best simulation during the verification period
grid()

legend("topright", legend=c("Qobs", "best.sim", "95PPU"), lty=c(1, 1, NA),
  pch=c(NA, NA, 15), col=c(Qobs.col, best.sim.col, bands.col),
  bty="n", cex = 1.2)

legend("topleft", legend=c(paste0("P-factor: ", round(pf, 2)),
  paste0("R-factor: ", round(rf, 2)) ),
  bty="n", cex = 1.2)

```


Figure 28: 95 Percent Prediction Uncertainty (95 PPU) for model simulations during the verification period.

10.3.5 Uncertainty in flow duration curve

The `fdcu` function from `hydroTSM` is used to plot the observed flow duration curve (FDC), the one of the *best* simulated streamflows, and the flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the verification period:

```
main.uncert <- paste0("FDC CemaNeige-GR6J model: ", Qobs.stationname, " (", Qobs.ID, ")" )
bands.col   <- "lightskyblue1"

par(mfrow=c(3, 1), mar = c(2, 3.5, 1, 1), oma=c(0, 0, 0, 0), mgp=c(2, 0.75, 0) )
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, bands.col=bands.col,
     main=main.uncert, log="") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, bands.col=bands.col,
     main="", log="y") # empty plotting area
grid()
fdcu(x=Qobs.zoo.ver, lband=q025, uband=q975, sim=Qsim.zoo.ver, bands.col=bands.col,
     main="", log="x") # empty plotting area
grid()
```


Figure 29: Flow duration curve of the observed (black line) and best simulated (blue line) streamflows. In addition, flow duration curves for the 2.5 and 97.5 weighted quantiles of model simulations obtained during the verification period. The upper panel is the normal flow duration curve, the middle panel has focus on low flows ($\log='y'$) and the lower panel has focus on high flows ($\log='x'$).

11 FAQ

11.1 How can I parallelise my computations?

In hydroPSO, parallel execution is controlled through the `parallel` element of the `control` list passed to `hydroPSO`. For R-based models such as `CemaNeige-GR6J`, this can reduce computing time when the model function is sufficiently expensive or when a large swarm and many iterations are used.

The following two code chunks illustrate how to run the same calibration without and with parallel computation. They use the minimal model function defined earlier and keep the same calibration settings, so that the difference is restricted to the execution mode.

```
parallel <- "none"
write2disk <- FALSE
set.seed(1000)
( t1 <- system.time(
  out <- hydroPSO(fn="hydromodInR",
    lower=lower, upper=upper, method="spso2011",
    control=list(write2disk=write2disk, MinMax="max", npart=80,
      maxit=50, normalise=TRUE, REPORT=10,
      parallel=parallel, reltol=1E-10),
    model.FUN = CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR,
    model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args
  )
)
)
```

```
## user system elapsed
## 27.055 0.123 27.217
```

```
parallel <- "parallel"
write2disk <- FALSE
set.seed(1000)
( t2 <- system.time(
  out <- hydroPSO(fn="hydromodInR",
    lower=lower, upper=upper, method="spso2011",
    control=list(write2disk=write2disk, MinMax="max", npart=80,
      maxit=50, normalise=TRUE, REPORT=10,
      parallel=parallel, reltol=1E-10),
    model.FUN = CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR,
    model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args
  )
)
)
```

```
## user system elapsed
## 43.005 12.044 15.687
```

The total reduction in the *elapsed times* (see `?proc.time`) when comparing the previous two running R processes was (as percentage):

```
reduction <- as.numeric(round(100 * (t1["elapsed"] - t2["elapsed"]) / t1["elapsed"], 1))
( paste0(reduction, "%") )
```

```
## [1] "42.4%"
```

The previous difference in execution time was important, because `hydroPSO` was executed without writing the output files to the hard drive and because single run of the `CemaNeige-GR6J` model is quite fast. This reduction in computation time can make an even more important difference for hydrological models with long running times.

Of course, for the same hydrological model and host machine, the total reduction in computation time will increase with increasing values of `par.nnodes`. However, if the value of `par.nnodes` is not so high (six or less), **the use of `parallel!=none` might not be a good idea**, because of the overhead associated to the communication between the cores/nodes and the main algorithm.

You can also run `verification` in parallel using the same previous approach:

```
out <- verification(fn = "hydromodInR",
  par = params,
  control = list(gof.name = "KGE2012", # Only used for plot titles
    MinMax = "max", # Are we looking for a minimum or maximum?
    do.plots = FALSE,
    write2disk = TRUE,
    parallel = "parallel",
    par.nnodes = 5,
    par.pkgs = c("hydroPSO", "hydroGOF", "hydroTSM",
      "zoo", "data.table"),
    verbose = TRUE),
  model.FUN = CemaNeigeGR6J_hydromodInR,
  model.FUN.args = model.FUN.args.ver
)
```

11.2 Why do I get some warnings after the calibration?

It is likely that you get some warnings after finishing the calibration of `CemaNeige-GR6J` with `hydroPSO`, as for example:

```
Param[4] (X4: unit hydrograph time constant [d]) < 0.50 X4 set to 0.50
```

If you want to know the meaning of this or other warnings that appear during calibration, please contact and report the warning to the maintainer of the [airGR](#) package.

11.3 Why the KGE values shown by `ggof` do not match the one obtained during the optimisation?

The KGE value shown by `ggof` uses `method="2009"`. If the KGE value obtained during the optimisation is different from the one shown by `ggof`, it is very likely because `method="2012"` was used for the computation of KGE during calibration.

11.4 Why do I get different results every time that I run `hydroPSO` with the same input data?

As mentioned in [Section 5](#), `hydroPSO` is a stochastic optimisation technique and, therefore, the initialisation of particle positions and the exploration of the parameter space are different every time that `hydroPSO` is

run. For reproducibility, use `set.seed` with a numeric argument (e.g., `set.seed(100)`) just before calling `hydroPSO`.

12 Software details

This tutorial was built under:

```
## [1] "aarch64-apple-darwin23"  
## [1] "R version 4.6.0 (2026-04-24)"  
## [1] "hydroPSO 0.5-58"  
## [1] "airGR 1.7.8"  
## [1] "hydroGOF 0.7-0"  
## [1] "hydroTSM 0.8-6"  
## [1] "zoo 1.8-15"
```

13 Version history

-) v0.4: May 31th, 2026
-) v0.3: May 28th, 2026
-) v0.2: Dec 07th, 2021
-) v0.1: June 16th, 2021

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